

NDAC/LO/153

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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, XXI

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This belated report was to give some important calibrations and statistics from preliminary 37-month solutions, to be used as guidance in the final solutions. This is now described in sections 1-4, while sections 5-7 describe the final CHF-generation and some calibration/solution results derived from these new data.

1. Preliminary 37-month CHF:s

The final CHF-generation had to await the final sphere-solution and was only recently completed. In the meantime, it was important to test the improved STDDBL/SEEKDBL programs (cf. NDAC/LO/152) on 'almost final' data, and last September I therefore made a quick extension of the existing 30-month CHF:s to 37 months. This was possible using most of the old intermediate results, only adding IDT- and attitude-data for the last months of the mission. This simplified CHF-generation then ran very smoothly, and 432 Mb of Case History Files (for identically the same 35082 systems described in NDAC/LO/152) were ready by September 30 last year.

2. Preliminary calibration solutions

The standard solution program SEEKDBL was then used on the (I)-CHF:s, which as expected gave mostly single-star solutions. Comparison with NDAC's sphere solution showed good agreement, although perhaps not quite as good as expected from the 30-month results. The original figures are shown in Table 1, and obviously the differences are a bit larger than those in Table 1 in NDAC/LO/152. This is partly a consequence of an increased number of common solutions, but the systematic-looking covariance-ratios do signify also some real problems with the covariance calibration.

To test this further, a round of 'half-observation' solutions (cf. NDAC/LO/151) were made this January for a sample of some 5500 'well-behaved' doubles. From the observed deviations between solutions made with alternate halves of the data, the solution sigmas can in principle be calibrated, but even the present large sample is insufficient for a satisfactory study. As in previous tests, different parameters behave differently as a function of magnitude and S_f (= 'normalized' χ^2 -fit to the observations), and it is not easy to arrive at a sensible calibration. After a lot(!) of experimenting, I settled for the following prescriptions.

First, it was necessary to decrease the C_i/n_{scan} -corrections (introduced because of systematic attitude-errors, cf. NDAC/LO/145). This is difficult, however, as it is based on comparisons with the sphere-solution sigmas which in themselves depend on some approximate adjustments. It was impossible to find C_i -values giving no residual n_{scan} -dependence, but values around 7, 5, 10 mas² in position and parallax, and 10, 7 (mas/yr)² in proper motion seemed reasonable. (Typically, the corrected covariance-ratios relative to the sphere solution slope 'upward' as a function of n_{scan} for α and μ_α , 'downward' for δ and μ_δ).

Then again, realizing that the 'observed' χ^2 -values (S_f) can not be rigorously corrected for the above variance-corrections, the S_f :s were instead first modified by a simple magnitude-equation to make the majority close to unity. The spread in the resulting S_f -distribution is large, probably because it is dominated by photometric effects. While the 'photometric' variances should therefore be multiplied by (the corrected) S_f , I found empirically that the

Table 1. Statistics for the differences between the 37-month DS(Oct 94)- and sphere solution results for stars in different magnitude-intervals. The absolute differences are given in mas (mas/yr), while the normalized differences have been divided by the sphere solution σ . Simple means and standard deviations for the covariance-ratios are also given.

Parameter	Hp	n	Abs diff		Norm diff		cov(DS)/cov(sph)	
			mean	stddev	mean	stddev	mean	stddev
α	< 7	705	-0.05(0.87)		-0.02(0.81)		1.22(0.42)	
δ	< 7	705	-0.04(0.63)		-0.05(0.78)		1.20(0.39)	
π	< 7	705	+0.02(0.90)		+0.02(0.73)		1.22(0.34)	
μ_α	< 7	705	-0.06(1.17)		-0.06(0.87)		1.72(0.66)	
μ_δ	< 7	705	-0.03(0.88)		-0.03(0.90)		1.45(0.55)	
α	7-10	3845	-0.02(0.89)		-0.02(0.68)		0.95(0.28)	
δ	7-10	3845	-0.01(0.68)		-0.01(0.68)		0.93(0.27)	
π	7-10	3845	+0.04(1.01)		+0.03(0.66)		0.94(0.24)	
μ_α	7-10	3845	-0.01(1.24)		-0.02(0.80)		1.26(0.44)	
μ_δ	7-10	3845	-0.01(0.92)		-0.01(0.77)		1.10(0.36)	
α	> 10	422	+0.05(1.66)		+0.02(0.67)		0.95(0.28)	
δ	> 10	422	-0.05(1.33)		-0.03(0.68)		0.93(0.27)	
π	> 10	422	-0.02(1.69)		-0.01(0.61)		0.94(0.24)	
μ_α	> 10	422	+0.22(2.22)		+0.08(0.76)		1.26(0.44)	
μ_δ	> 10	422	+0.05(1.64)		+0.04(0.77)		1.10(0.36)	

astrometric variances are better scaled by about S_f to the 2/3 power. With these starting assumptions, I then derived 'magnitude-equations' giving corrected solution-sigmas that agree with the observed scatter between the 'half-obs' solutions.

Because of the broad S_f -distribution, a rather simple 'asymmetric parabola' was used to make it approximately independent of magnitude, viz.

$$S_f(\text{corr}) \equiv S_c = \begin{cases} S_f/[1.5 + 0.12(Hp - 8.3)^2] & \text{for } Hp < 8.3 \\ S_f/[1.5 + 0.03(Hp - 8.3)^2] & \text{for } Hp > 8.3 \end{cases}$$

Then, to sufficient accuracy, two different magnitude-equations are sufficient. For the photometric and 'relative' astrometric parameters, the solution covariances are multiplied by approximately

$$f_1(Hp) = 1.50 + 0.20(Hp - 8.3)^2$$

For the 'absolute' astrometric data, the covariances have to be multiplied (after the C_i/n_{scan} correction!) instead by

$$f_2(Hp) = 1.20 + 0.10|Hp - 8.3|$$

(All the time, the changes are made in the diagonal elements of the covariance matrix, while the correlations are preserved.)

This is purely empirical and ad hoc, but as the 'half-observation' solutions are the best internal check available and since the original solutions do show definite magnitude-effects, such calibrations have to be made. With the corrections applied, the normalized rms deviations for all twelve solution parameters are within about 20 % of unity when the data are separated according to magnitude, S_c , separation and magnitude difference, and I don't deem it meaningful to go further with the preliminary data.

Returning to the single-star comparison with the sphere-solution, these new calibrated DS sigmas could also be compared with the sphere-solution ones, giving the data in Table 2. Also

given are similar 'calibration' ratios derived by Lindegren from 'half-obs' sphere solutions, showing as good an agreement as might be hoped for, considering the completely different solution- and calibration methods used. There is an obvious remaining magnitude-trend that can not easily be accounted for. (The DS calibration says the faint-star sigmas are too small, while the single-star data shows an opposite trend).

Table 2. Median sigma-ratios DS/sphere(orig) from solutions for single stars in different magnitude-intervals. In parenthesis are given the corrective ratios sphere(corr)/-sphere(orig) derived by Lindegren, which ideally should be equal.

H_p	< 5.5	5.5 - 7.5	7.5 - 8.5	8.5 - 9.5	9.5 - 10.5	> 10.5
nobs	99	1020	1589	1401	427	252
$\langle S_c \rangle$	1.00	1.00	1.03	1.01	1.01	0.99
α	0.82(0.84)	0.84(0.85)	0.85(0.88)	0.88(0.91)	0.92(0.93)	0.98(0.95)
δ	0.84(0.87)	0.83(0.85)	0.84(0.88)	0.88(0.90)	0.93(0.92)	0.98(0.94)
π	0.81(0.86)	0.81(0.86)	0.83(0.88)	0.86(0.90)	0.92(0.94)	0.97(0.94)
μ_α	0.83(0.88)	0.85(0.91)	0.87(0.92)	0.91(0.95)	0.95(0.95)	1.01(0.96)
μ_δ	0.82(0.88)	0.83(0.88)	0.86(0.91)	0.90(0.93)	0.97(0.96)	1.00(0.96)
$\langle DS/(sph)_0 \rangle$	0.82	0.83	0.85	0.89	0.94	0.99
$\langle (sph)_c/(sph)_0 \rangle$	0.87	0.87	0.89	0.92	0.94	0.95
$\langle DS/(sph)_c \rangle$	0.94	0.95	0.96	0.97	1.00	1.04

3. Preliminary 37-month solutions

With the 'new' solution-programs described in NDAC/LO/152, a large-scale round of solutions was performed. Because there are 'coarse' and 'detailed' search-modes, because SEEKDBL may be run on stars with no STDDBL solution, because new program-changes (bug-fixes and refinements) were introduced *and* because of 'normal' computer-problems, the administration of these runs was not at all trivial. The full series includes also the 'multiple' CHF:s (solved by SEEKDBL with no a priori data for single-pointing and by STDDBL assuming two wide components for the 2-pointing systems), although many of these will later be put through a special STDMUL-program.

Each of some fifty different runs (keeping the HP 9000/720 continuously busy for most of November and December) gave two sequential result-files (one with component epoch magnitudes for the automatically recognized variables), and it was imperative to collect all these data in some sensible way. For this, I created two large direct-access files (again a special one for the magnitude-data) so that I can have immediate access to the collected results (including earlier 18-month and 30-month solutions) for any specific object. From this database I can also make printouts with selected results, and some of these has gone to FAST for comparison purposes.

The covariances in these data were originally calibrated by old 30-month prescriptions, but after the above re-calibration, all covariances in the result-files were (again rather laboriously) re-derived. The relations between the old and the improved sigmas are clearly complex and magnitude-dependent, but in the mean, the 'absolute' sigmas have been decreased by some 8 %, the 'relative' sigmas have been decreased by about 10 %, while the photometric ones have been increased by about 10 %.

4. Solution statistics

There are many tests and statistics to be made from the solution data, but since so many unexpected problems have taken too much time, only some basic ones have been completed. The raw solution-numbers are not very illuminating, because obviously one has to apply 'cut-off'-limits where the solutions cease to be trustworthy. In several previous studies, I have arrived at limits in Δm_{eff} around 4.5, but in the present solution programs, I have introduced also a quantity S_s (solution significance), being *roughly* the difference between the normalized χ^2 for a single-star and a double-star solution, divided by an approximate mean error. A positive S_s says the double-star solution fits better than a single-star solution, but values below 3 are not very significant. From the distribution of the solutions in Δm_{eff} and S_s , I have introduced a 'quality-index' I_q that in these first tests is defined by

$$I_q = \begin{cases} 3, & \text{if } S_s > 10 \text{ and } \Delta m_{\text{eff}} < 3.0 \\ 2, & \text{if } S_s > \sqrt{10} \text{ and } \Delta m_{\text{eff}} < 4.0 \text{ and } I_q \neq 3 \\ 1, & \text{if } S_s > 1 \text{ and } \Delta m_{\text{eff}} < 4.5 \text{ and } I_q \neq 2 \text{ or } 3 \\ 0, & \text{if } S_s < 1 \text{ or } \Delta m_{\text{eff}} > 4.5 \end{cases}$$

(Generally, the solutions with $I_q=0$ should be considered mostly spurious, and the ones with $I_q=1$ 'poor'). One can now make the crude statistics in Table 3 for the -94 solutions. Most of the 'bad' ($I_q=0,1$) solutions are (as expected) for 'new' systems, which also have a much larger percentage of variable components. (These latter figures are only illustrative, however, because they depend so heavily on the threshold used).

Table 3. The number of solutions in the different quality-classes, separated according to the a priori knowledge about the system. The numbers in parentheses are the percentages of systems with 'variable components'.

	$I_q = 0$	$I_q = 1$	$I_q = 2$	$I_q = 3$
known a prio	448(4)	580(4)	1449(3)	6371(2)
no a prio data	2188(7)	2102(13)	2455(19)	2006(6)

A more illuminating test comes from running 'good' known doubles with SEEKDBL (and thus *no* a priori information). An input-list with about 6350 objects was made from the stars where the STDDBL solution agrees with the a priori data to within about 0.3 arcsec, hopefully meaning that 'slit-errors' are mostly absent. SEEKDBL was then run with the standard 'search-radius' 5.2 arcsec, which means that, ideally, all stars with smaller separation should be recovered.

The real result sometimes approaches this ideal. Out of 4850 objects with $\rho < 5.2$ arcsec, some 85 % had the relative x,y positions and the magnitude-difference in the SEEKDBL-solution within 3σ of the original STDDBL data. The statistics may be further divided according to separation and magnitude-difference, giving the results in Table 4. Although there are some problems for equal-magnitude stars, 'intermediate Δm ' objects are solved very efficiently at all separations. As before, the failure-rate does not reach 50% until about $\Delta m_{\text{eff}} = 4.5$.

For stars with true separations 5.2-10 arcsec, a SEEKDBL solution with approximately correct Δm is mostly found, but with an erroneous separation (below 5.2 arcsec). A plot of these false solutions shows very clearly that they are predominantly at multiples of 1.2 arcsec from the true one (Fig. 1). Going to the 2-pointing systems, the solution Δm is now closer to the real one plus the IFOV attenuation, but the relative position offsets are too large to fall clearly at grid-step positions.

The most important conclusion from Table 4 is that poor a priori positions is *not* a major problem for the known doubles, because the correct solution is mostly found anyway. For the

new doubles, which are expected to have small separations and/or large magnitude-differences, grid-step errors will be unavoidably and increasingly present as the magnitude-difference is increased, and this is in fact the main effect setting the detection-limit in Δm_{eff} .

Table 4. Percentages of 'good'(within 3σ), 'other' and 'failed' SEEKDBL solutions (no aprio information) for systems with different separations and magnitude differences.

Δm_{eff}	< 0.5	0.5 – 1.5	1.5 – 3.0	3.0 – 4.0	4.0 – 4.5	4.5 – 5.0
$n(\rho < 0.5)$	99	513	480	32	6	7
within 3σ (%)	84	85	86	47:	33::	57::
other sol(%)	4	6	11	47:	67::	29::
no sol (%)	12	10	3	6:	0::	14::
$n(\rho = 0.5 - 1.5)$	386	545	582	142	23	6
within 3σ (%)	67	88	98	91	61:	33::
other sol(%)	16	7	1	8	39:	67::
no sol (%)	17	5	1	1	0:	0::
$n(\rho = 1.5 - 5.2)$	355	484	641	383	128	86
within 3σ (%)	71	85	94	93	76	43
other sol(%)	19	5	1	6	23	41
no sol (%)	10	11	5	2	1	16

error in SEEK rel pos (real sep=5-10 arcsec)

Fig. 1. Spurious SEEKDBL solutions for known doubles with $\rho > 5.2$ arcsec.

5. Final CHF-generation

After the final 37-month sphere solution was finished in April, a new set of Case History Files have been derived, with several improvements. In NDAC:s sphere-solutions, Lennart Lindgren solves for a significant 6:th harmonic deviation in the set-solution abscissae. Sine and cosine amplitudes are given for each set, and the corresponding phase-shifts are now applied in the CHF-generation. Another major improvement is the introduction of short time-scale zero-point shifts in the photometric calibration. Other changes in the program concerns the colour used in the geometric calibrations, a new model for the 'constant chromaticity' (with one coefficient for each set), plus a new format to save an 'effective attitude-uncertainty' from the sphere solution. I have also corrected several smaller bugs related to e.g. the orbit-numbering and the sun-pointing intervals.

As for the selection of objects, the (ideal) goal to make CHF:s for all HIP-numbers has been again postponed. However, in order to have CHF:s for as many 'interesting' objects as possible, the original selection used for the 30- and preliminary 37-month runs has been enlarged by two important additions. First, some 2200 objects with FAST DS solutions (but so far no CHF:s) were included, and secondly, all stars without (NDAC) sphere solution. Of these latter, only some 180 objects were not previously selected for one reason or another.

The modifications and debugging necessitated several re-runs, but on May 4:th, I had collected 4.35 million FOVC:s from 2321 sets into 37374 CHF:s. (There may still be some useable data missing, because attitudes are available for 2324 sets, but this has not yet been investigated in detail. The september preliminary run gave data only from 2287 sets, so the present run is a definite improvement in completeness also).

Not part of the CHF-generation proper is the flagging of observations disturbed by a star in the other FOV. A star-wise list of these occasions was obtained from RGO, and I have simply put in in a direct-access file that is checked when data are read from a CHF to a solution program. From the disturbing star magnitude and distance from the field center (given by RGO), I calculate an 'effective dm' and simply reject all observations where it is below 5. (A larger dm has probably little effect, but in the present solutions, these marginally disturbed observations are not used either).

6. New calibration solutions

Again, one may first check that SEEKDBL gives single-star solutions agreeing with the (independent) sphere solution. Table 5 shows the improvement from the preliminary data in Table 1, but for the brightest stars, the agreement is still a bit worse than expected. (The covariance-ratios are calculated *after* the calibrations described below, and here there may be a problem in the faint end).

Then, for the covariance-calibration, I have finally realized that the 'C/nscan'-model is too crude an approximation. A rigorous solution is very complicated, however, because of attitude error-correlations between FOVC:s with approximately the same scan-geometry. (In retrospect, it might have been better to use one 'normal point' per 'scan', but then the photometry variations become more problematic to administrate...) As a working alternative, I now make and solve for each star a set of normal equations derived from the geometry and 'effective attitude uncertainty' at each scan. This rather ad hoc procedure (especially the definition of a 'scan') gives a 'systematic' variance (to be added to the solution variances) of the same order of magnitude as the previous C/nscan, but with a better relation to the individual scanning geometries. A good indication that this model is sensible comes from comparisons with the sphere solution variances. There is now little or no variation with nscan, and all five astrometric parameters behave similarly.

With this basis, the magnitude-equations were re-derived from new 'half-observation' solutions. Preliminarily, I now use (cf. Sect 2 above)

$$S_f(\text{corr}) \equiv S_c = \begin{cases} S_f/[1.5 + 0.14(8.0 - Hp)^2] & \text{for } Hp < 8.0 \\ S_f/[1.5 + 0.04(Hp - 8.0)^2] & \text{for } Hp > 8.0 \end{cases}$$

$$f_1(Hp) = 1.50 + 0.20(Hp - 8.0)^2$$

$$f_2(Hp) = \begin{cases} 1.20 - 0.02(8.0 - Hp) & \text{for } Hp < 8.0 \\ 1.20 + 0.14(Hp - 8.0) & \text{for } Hp > 8.0 \end{cases}$$

Again, these values are a compromise between the 'half-obs' and single-star data. There are still opposing trends for the faintest stars, as may be seen from Tables 6 and 7.

Table 5. Statistics for the differences between the 37-month DS (May -95) and sphere solution results for stars in different magnitude-intervals. The absolute differences are given in mas (mas/yr), while the normalized differences have been divided by the sphere solution σ . Simple means and standard deviations for the covariance-ratios are also given.

Parameter	Hp	n	Abs diff		Norm diff		cov(DS)/cov(sph)	
			mean	stddev	mean	stddev	mean	stddev
α	< 7	691	+0.00(0.72)		+0.03(0.90)		1.01(0.21)	
δ	< 7	690	-0.03(0.50)		-0.05(0.80)		1.09(0.25)	
π	< 7	691	+0.03(0.77)		+0.04(0.78)		0.99(0.18)	
μ_α	< 7	689	-0.03(0.91)		-0.05(0.90)		0.97(0.23)	
μ_δ	< 7	691	-0.00(0.69)		+0.00(0.89)		1.00(0.24)	
α	7-10	3762	-0.05(0.64)		-0.04(0.61)		1.04(0.21)	
δ	7-10	3761	-0.01(0.53)		-0.01(0.62)		1.09(0.22)	
π	7-10	3762	-0.00(0.79)		+0.00(0.60)		1.03(0.19)	
μ_α	7-10	3761	-0.02(0.85)		-0.03(0.66)		1.02(0.20)	
μ_δ	7-10	3761	+0.00(0.69)		+0.00(0.66)		1.04(0.21)	
α	> 10	422	-0.14(1.44)		-0.07(0.60)		1.22(0.47)	
δ	> 10	422	-0.07(1.11)		-0.03(0.60)		1.23(0.42)	
π	> 10	422	-0.09(1.72)		-0.03(0.61)		1.22(0.47)	
μ_α	> 10	422	+0.00(1.88)		-0.02(0.63)		1.20(0.43)	
μ_δ	> 10	422	+0.04(1.33)		+0.03(0.60)		1.20(0.41)	

Table 6. Mean rms-values for the normalized differences between 'half-obs' solutions using the calibrated sigmas described in the text. Data separated according to magnitude.

Hp	< 5.5	5.5 - 7.5	7.5 - 8.5	8.5 - 9.5	9.5 - 10.5	> 10.5
nobs	43	257	668	2683	358	31
$\langle S_c \rangle$	1.05	0.97	1.01	1.04	1.08	1.03
α	1.14	1.01	0.98	1.00	1.03	1.24
δ	1.06	0.97	0.99	0.99	1.07	0.96
π	0.79	0.96	0.94	0.94	0.93	1.00
μ_α	0.85	0.96	1.02	0.98	0.92	1.17
μ_δ	0.96	1.03	0.97	0.97	0.98	1.09
$\langle abs \rangle$	0.96	0.99	0.98	0.98	0.99	1.09
$\Delta\alpha$	0.91	0.99	0.99	0.98	0.94	0.99
$\Delta\delta$	1.13	0.97	0.97	1.00	0.97	0.96
$\Delta\pi$	0.91	0.96	0.95	0.98	1.02	0.84
$\Delta\mu_\alpha$	1.03	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.92	1.00
$\Delta\mu_\delta$	1.15	0.96	0.98	1.00	0.98	0.87
$\langle rel \rangle$	1.03	0.97	0.97	0.99	0.97	0.93
Hp	1.13	0.92	0.97	1.01	1.10	0.75
ΔHp	0.98	0.85	0.99	0.99	1.11	0.82
$\langle phot \rangle$	1.06	0.88	0.98	1.00	1.10	0.78

Table 7. Median sigma-ratios DS/sphere from solutions for single stars in different magnitude-intervals.

H_p	< 5.5	5.5 – 7.5	7.5 – 8.5	8.5 – 9.5	9.5 – 10.5	> 10.5
nobs	114	1075	1639	1368	412	268
$\langle S_c \rangle$	1.01	1.04	1.03	1.00	0.96	0.95
α	0.97	0.99	0.99	1.01	1.04	1.03
δ	1.01	1.02	1.02	1.03	1.05	1.07
π	0.96	0.98	0.99	1.01	1.04	1.07
μ_α	0.96	0.97	0.98	1.01	1.04	1.07
μ_δ	0.96	0.98	0.99	1.01	1.04	1.06
$\langle \text{DS}/(\text{sph}) \rangle$	0.97	0.99	0.99	1.01	1.04	1.05

Further calibrations of both the solutions and their covariances should ideally be made using ground-based speckle- and CCD-observations, but no large-scale collection of the requisite data has been made.

7. The final solutions

It is still administratively complex to run STDDBL and/or SEEKDBL for all the available CHF:s. There are many different ‘categories’ of systems that have to be treated differently, a solution failing with one set of a priori input is sometimes to be run with another set or with a ‘free’ search, and so on. To these real difficulties are then added the normal competition for CPU- time together with unavoidable computer shutdowns, so that at least two months of real time will be needed to complete the task.

So far, I have completed about half of the SEEKDBL-run for the standard ‘suspect’ category of stars. In the 30-month and preliminary 37-month solutions, the ‘marginal’ new doubles (large Δm :s) had a strangely uneven distribution in separation, with peaks just above and below (and minima at exactly) an integral number of slit-periods. This effect was rather problematic, because runs on similar known doubles could solve them at any separation, and the ‘bands’ could therefore not be removed as totally spurious. In the new solutions, the effect is much reduced, which must tentatively be ascribed to the improved CHF:s. As before, there *are* fewer solutions at separations around half-integer slit-periods (especially 1.7-2.0 arcsec), and more work is needed to understand and/or ‘calibrate’ this non-uniformity in the detection efficiency.

Also, I have made a special run for some 1000 of the stars where FAST finds a DS solution and NDAC does not even suspect them as non-single. Using the FAST DS parameters as start values, the STDDBL program finds at most 25 double-star solutions, with less than 10 reasonably close to the FAST ones. For almost 95 % of these stars, the NDAC output is an uncomplicated single-star solution.

8. Conclusions

Because a lot of time has been spent in various ‘cleaning/debugging’- operations, the visible progress of NDAC:s DS reductions has been rather slow since the last DSWG meeting. Hopefully, with the final CHF-generation completed and the solutions in good progress, the delay is not too severe. Data for many ‘easy’ doubles (requiring no parameter grid-searches) will soon be available for merging-experiments, and most of the DS-results should be available in early July.